

THE PISAURIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

The Pisauridae is a large cosmopolitan family of spiders represented in South Africa by 13 genera and 37 species. The family has diverse life-styles and have reverted from web-building to free-living wanderers. They are found in a variety of habitats and are common inhabitants of grassland, savanna, desert and forest areas. The pisaurid female carries the egg cocoon beneath her sternum held by her chelicerae and palpi. Just before the young emerge the female constructs a framework of silk, known as a nursery web in which she deposits the egg cocoon. More than 90% of the species have a wide distribution and is listed as Least Concern. Of these species 27 spp. (73%) are African endemics, three are known from southern Africa and seven are South African endemics. Of the South African endemics three species are known only from the type locality and is listed at Data Deficient. No species are presently flagged as of special concern. Two genera *Tapinothelella*, 1909 and *Walrencea* Blandin, 1979 are endemic to South Africa. The taxonomy of the Pisauridae of South Africa is only partly resolved. We do not have any records of *Dolomedes* spp. from South Africa but they might be here. Of the 828 records in the National Collection of Arachnida 26% have not been identified to species level.

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* South African species not listed in the World Spider Catalog 2020

FAMILY PISAURIDAE

The Pisauridae is a large cosmopolitan family of spiders represented in South Africa by 13 genera and 37 species of which seven are South African endemics (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAMES: Nursery Web Spiders

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: 8-30 mm (males more slender and longer legs). Colour: cryptic with carapace frequently decorated with white longitudinal bands or symmetrical patterns of black on brown or grey on black, abdomen with paler longitudinal bands or spots. Carapace longer than wide; in some genera with blunt tubercles on the anterolateral edge of clypeus; eyes eight but pattern variable: arranged in 2 rows (4:4), 3 rows (4.2.2) or 4 rows (2.2.2.2) with at least one pair of eyes on shallow tubercles; some genera e.g. *Rothus* with cluster of setae between anterior eyes; number of teeth on chelicerae vary between genera. Abdomen variable from elongated to round oval tapering towards back. Legs relatively long; usually with spines.

LIFE STYLE: The family has diverse life-styles and has reverted from web-building to free-living wanderers. They are found in a variety of habitats and are common inhabitants of grassland, savanna, desert and forest areas. The pisaurid female carries the egg cocoon beneath her sternum held by her chelicerae and palpi. Just before the young emerge the female constructs a framework of silk, known as a nursery web in which she deposits the egg cocoon. After emerging from the egg cocoon the young, stay in this nursery web before they disperse, hence their common name nursery web spiders.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Some of the genera were revised by Blandin (1974-1978) and Sierwald (1987-1997).

Afropisaura sp. Peter Webb

Charminus sp. Ernst Klimsa

Chiasmopes sp. John Richter

Cispius sp. Peter Webb

Euprosthénops sp. Peter Webb

Euprosthénopsis sp. Peter Webb

eyes in 2 rows (4:4)

3 rows (4.2.2)

4 rows (2.2.2.2)

EXAMPLES OF EYE PATTERNS

QUICK KEY TO THE SOUTH AFRICAN GENERA

"SHORT" ABDOMEN

Afropisaura

Charminus

Cispius

Euphrostenopsis

Nilus

Rothus

Walrencea

"LONG" ABDOMEN

Chiasmopes spp.

Euphrostenops

Hygropoda

Maypacius

GENUS *AFROPISAURA* Blandin, 1976

The genus *Afropisaura* described by Blandin (1976) is represented by three African species. They were formerly placed in the genus *Pisaura* (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAME: Afropisaura Nursery Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Afropisaura valida* (Simon, 1886)

MORPHOLOGY: Body size female 9-14 mm, male 11-13 mm, males with longer legs than females. Carapace as wide as long; narrower in eye region; eight eyes in two rows (2:2); anterior eye row slightly procurved; posterior row recurved; posterior row slightly wider than anterior row; anterior median eyes smallest; chelicerae with three equally-sized cheliceral teeth. Abdomen elongated, tapering towards back; usually with plumose setae. Legs: three claws; legs relatively long, sometimes slightly laterigrade; with setae on patellae, femora, tibiae and metatarsi; tarsi with trichobothria in two rows, or scattered; trochanters deeply notched.

LIFESTYLE: They are free-living plant dwellers. The female carries the egg sac below her body and constructs a nursery webs for the spiderlings (Blandin 1979). *Afropisaura* is one of the pisaurid genera that is frequently sampled sweeping grass and low vegetation.

TAXONOMY: Revised by Blandin (1976) and Sierwald (1997) but unfortunately specimens from southern Africa were not included in the revision.

Habitus after Blandin (1976)

Eyes after Blandin (1976)

Afropisaura sp. Photo Peter Webb

Afropisaura ducis (Strand, 1913)

COMMON NAME: East Africa Afropisaura Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Strand (1913) as *Pisaura ducis* from Lake Kivu in East Africa. It has a wide distribution throughout Africa. In South Africa recorded from four provinces (EOO=284 578 km²; AOO=24 km²; 16-1513 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living nursery-web spiders that are commonly found on vegetation at night. Their movements are erratic as they move swiftly around in leaps or jumps. Sampled from the Grassland, Savanna and Thicket Biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: West, Central, East Africa and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Thyspunt 12 km WNW Cape St Francis (-34.2056, 24.7083); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Umhlanga Rocks (-29.73, 31.07). **Limpopo:** Lephalale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71); Gundani Forest (-22.655, 30.532). **Gauteng:** Irene Veld (field opposite Gem Village) (-25.89, 28.23).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in the Mountain Zebra National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Blandin (1976) and Sierwald (1997) and known from both sexes.

Afropisaura ducis female from Irene Photo P. Webb

Afropisaura ducis female from Lephalale Photo P. Webb

After Blandin (1976)

Afropisaura ducis female from Gundani Photo P. Webb

Afropisaura rothiformis (Strand, 1908)

COMMON NAME: Common Afropisaura Grass Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Strand (1908) as *Pisaura rothiformis* from the Cameroon. It has a wide distribution throughout Africa. In South Africa sampled from seven provinces (EOO=457 445 km²; AOO=76 km²; 1-1706 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range it is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living nursery-web spiderS that are commonly found on vegetation at night. Their movements are erratic as they move swiftly in leaps or jumps. They are sampled with sweep nets and were recorded from the Grassland, Savanna and Thicket Biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Burundi, Cameroon, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Ethiopia, Nigeria, Somalia, Tanzania, Uganda and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mkambati Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97); Addo National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **Gauteng:** Irene (field opposite Gem Village) (-25.89, 28.23); Wonderboom (-25.69, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Loteni Nature Reserve (-29.47, 29.52); Charters Creek Champ (soccer field) (-28.1991, 32.4143); iSimangaliso Wetland Park Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Oribi Gorge Nature Reserve (-30.71, 30.26). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Kruger National Park, Shingwedzi (15 km SW) (-23.17, 31.3); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.17, 30.25); Vyeboom (-23.1439, 30.3797); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.038, 29.442). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-25.00, 31.97); Kruger National Park (Shabeni) (-25.123, 31.237); Kruger National Park (Numbi) (-25.15, 31.19); Kruger National Park (Satara) (-24.38, 31.78). **North West:** Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Western Cape:** Cederberg Wilderness Area Sneekop West, 1700 (-32.34, 19.14).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is recorded from 11 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes, revised by Blandin (1976) and Sierwald (1997).

After Blandin (1976)

After Roewer (1955)

Afropisaura rothiformis Photo Hannes Mitchell

GENUS *CHARMINUS* Thorell, 1899

The African genus *Charminus* described by Thorell (1899) is known from nine species and one subspecies (World Spider Catalog 2020) of which four are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAME: Charminus Nursery-web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Charminus camerunensis* Thorell, 1899

MORPHOLOGY: Total body size female and male 7.8–9.7 mm. Female slightly larger than male, male with longer legs. Carapace longer than wide; narrower in eye region; both eye rows recurved; anterior row only slightly shorter than posterior row; anterior eyes slightly smaller than posterior eyes; three cheliceral teeth some individuals with four; teeth unequal in size (equally-sized in *Charminus ambiguus*). Abdomen oval. Legs pale or banded. Male palp with embolus long and whip like; retrolateral tibial apophysis simple, perpendicular, tip pointed.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant dwellers.

TAXONOMY: Revised by Blandin (1978) and Sierwald (1997). *Charminus* and *Cispius* morphologically very similar.

After Blandin(1978)

Eye pattern

3-teeth

Charminus ambiguus

Charminus atomarius

Charminus natalensis

Charminus aethiopicus

Charminus sp. from Hoedspruit Photo Peter Webb

Charminus sp. from Hoedspruit Photo Andre Coetzee

Charminus aethiopicus (Caporiacco, 1939)

COMMON NAME: East Africa Charminus Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Caporiacco (1939) as *Cispius aethiopicus* from Ethiopia. It has been recorded from 11 African countries. In South Africa recorded from two provinces (EOO= 21 103 km²; AOO=36 km²; 131-677 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Charminus species are commonly found inhabiting grasses herbs and low-growing shrubs especially in shaded areas. They are sampled with sweep nets from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Eleven African countries and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park near Rietbokpan (-22.93, 31.02); Kruger National Park (Pafuri) (-22.4224, 31.0361). **Mpumalanga:** Nelspruit, Ou Stal, ARC-ITSC (-25.47, 30.96); Lowveld National Botanical Garden (-25.47, 31.00); Kruger National Park (Sabiepoort) (-25.19, 32.2); Kruger National Park (Skukuza-Malelane B03U) (-25.1826, 31.6228); Kruger National Park (Skukuza-Malelane B03L) (-25.1094, 31.6235); Kruger National Park (Skukuza-Malelane) (-25.1144, 31.5143); Kruger National Park (Vutomi) (-24.61, 31.79).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. In South Africa it is protected the Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020) and Lowveld National Botanical Garden.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Sierwald (1997). Known from both sexes.

After Capriacco (1939)

After Caporiacco (1941)

Charminus aethiopicus male Photo ASD

Charminus ambiguus (Lessert, 1925)

COMMON NAME: Umbilo Charminus Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Lessert (1925) as *Cispius ambiguus* from Umbilo in KwaZulu-Natal. The species has been recorded from three African countries. In South Africa recorded from two provinces (EOO=164 358 km²; AOO=40 km²; 22-1362 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Specimens have been observed early in the morning when they run through and over the grass with great rapidity taking tremendous leaps. They disappear during the warmer parts of the day. They were sampled with sweep nets from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Tanzania, Malawi and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: Richards Bay 15 km N (-28.78, 32.10); Umbilo (-29.88, 30.96); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83); St. Lucia Wetland Park (-27.58, 32.67).

Limpopo: Swadini Nature Reserve (-22.992, 30.257); Entabeni Nature Reserve (-22.4237, 30.9108); Entabeni Forest (-23.00, 30.23); Tshulu (Venda) (-22.580, 30.809); Vaalwater (-24.29, 28.11); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Farm Malta (-24.17, 30.25); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Farm Balloon (-24.2, 30.34); Wallers Camp Pafuri River Camp (-22.424, 30.911); Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the following protected areas: Swadini Nature Reserve, Entabeni Nature Reserve and Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Blandin (1978) and known from both sexes. Species recognized by uniform brown grey carapace and abdomen dorsum with brown pattern, pale ventrally. Carapace with white marginal band, legs pale.

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Epigyne after Blandin (1978)

Charminus ambiguus from Kloof Photo P. Webb

Palp after Lessert (1925)

Charminus ambiguus from St Lucia Photo E. Klimsa

Charminus atomarius (Lawrence, 1942)

COMMON NAME: Umhlali Charminus Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described Lawrence (1942) as *Cispius atomarius* from Umhlali in KwaZulu-Natal. The species has been recorded from four African countries. In South Africa recorded from two provinces (EOO=24 745 km²; AOO=28 km²; 43-839 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They are found inhabiting grasses, herbs and low-growing shrubs especially in shaded areas. They are active at night and are usually sampled with sweep nets from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, Mozambique, Tanzania and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Umhlali (-29.47, 31.22); Ithala Nature Reserve (-27.51, 31.23); uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.6093, 32.2273); Alverstone near Hillcrest (-29.77, 30.73). **Limpopo:** Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Species protected in Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2009), Ithala Nature Reserve and uMkhuze Game Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Blandin (1978) and known from both sexes. Legs pale lightly banded; abdomen with dark pattern bordered by white, sometimes with pair of white spots. Carapace with median pale band bordered by two darker bands.

Epigyne and habitus
Photo ASD

Charminus atomarius from Alverstone KZN
Photo P. Webb

Epigyne and palp after
Blandin (1978)

Charminus atomarius from Hoedspruit
Photo P. Webb

Charminus natalensis (Lawrence, 1947)

COMMON NAME: Natal Charminus Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Lawrence (1947) as *Cispus natalensis* from Umfolosi Drift. Sampled from several localities in the KwaZulu-Natal (EOO=6 159 km²; AOO=20km²; 6-232m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range, however it is highly likely to be under collected and much natural habitat exists within its current range, therefore it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant dwellers that are commonly found in grasses herbs and low-growing shrubs especially in shaded areas. They are active at night and easily sampled with sweep nets from the Forest and Savanna Biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Hell's Gate (-28.00, 32.48); Manguzi, KwaNganase (-27.58, 32.45); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94; 32.47); Umfolozi Nature Reserve, Umfolosi Drift (-28.3, 31.76; Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species that is protected in the Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006), Tembe Elephant Park, Umfolozi Nature Reserve and Hluhluwe Nature Reserve. But more sampling is needed to collect the male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Blandin (1978) and known only from the female.

Charminus natalensis from Hluhluwe GR Photo Ernst Klimsa

After Blandin (1978)

Epigyne and habitus Photo ASD)

Charminus natalensis from Umhlanga Photo Peter

GENUS *CHIASMOPES* Pavesi, 1883

The genus *Chiasmopes* described by Pavesi (1883) is known from four African species (World Spider Catalog 2020). All four are recorded from South Africa.

COMMON NAME: Chiasmopes Nursery-Web Spiders

MORPHOLOGY: Size TL 10-13 mm. Carapace longer than wide, decorated with symmetrical patterns or longitudinal stripes; eight eyes arranged in four rows (2:2:2:2); anterior row very strongly procurved; anterior lateral eyes close together on shallow tubercles on the edge of the clypeus; median eyes smallest; median band of pale hairs running out into a crest between the eyes; posterior margin of chelicerae with three teeth. Abdomen elongate-oval tapers posteriorly; nearly four times as long as broad. Legs are relatively long; 1243; slightly laterigrade, with numerous spines; colour variable, uniformly yellow to dark brown, mottled brown or with dark bands; three claws.

LIFESTYLE: One of the sheet-web pisaurids that construct their webs in vegetation close to the ground, especially between short shrubs and bushes, but occasionally also between large grass tussocks. The sheet-like web consists of many criss-crossing silk threads.

TAXONOMY. Revised by Blandin (1977). It is the senior synonym of *Spencerella* Pocock, 1898 (World Spider Catalog 2020).

Chiasmopes lineatus Photo Linda Wiese

Chiasmopes namaquensis Photo Linda Wiese

Eye pattern *Chiasmopes lineatus* after Blandin (1974)

Chiasmopes signatus Photo John Richter

Chiasmopes hystrix (Berland, 1922)

COMMON NAME: Ethiopia Chiasmopes Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Berland (1922) as *Maypaci* *hystrix* from Ethiopia. It has been recorded from two African countries. In South Africa sampled from Mpumalanga (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1080 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: A sheet-web pisaurids that construct their webs in vegetation close to the ground especially in short shrubs and bushes but occasionally also between grass tussocks. Sampled from the Grassland and Savanna Biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Ethiopia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Mpumalanga*: Ohrigstad (-24.74, 30.58).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species due to the wide geographical range. But more sampling needed to confirm presence of species in South Africa.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Blandin (1977). Known from only the female. Colour: cephalothorax decorated in the middle with a light fawn band, covered with very white hairs, attenuated in front where it is extended by a brush of white hairs between the posterior median eyes; the sides of this band of a darker fawn, veined black, edges; fawn-red chelicera more or less spotted with black, as well as the maxillary blades; sternum with a median white line; on the sides of this line, two blackish bands, tawny edges; legs with dark femora, the others segments fawn with the two anterior pairs black; grey abdomen striped fawn and stained black; pubescence white and grey, silky, felted; on the sternum black setae, on the legs and abdomen, in the middle pubescence, small stiff setae (Berland (1922)

After Blandin (1977)

After Berland (1922)

Chiasmopes lineatus (Pocock, 1898)

COMMON NAME: Striped Chiasmopes Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Pocock (1898) as *Spencerella lineata* from Durban in South Africa. It has been recorded from several African countries including Swaziland and South Africa. In South Africa recorded from seven provinces (EOO=950 916 km²; AOO=104 km²; 17-2102 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range it is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Sheet-web pisaurids that construct their webs in vegetation close to the ground especially in short shrubs and bushes but occasionally also between longer grass tussocks. The sheet-web consists of many criss-crossing silk threads. They are active at night. Sampled from the Fynbos, Forest, Grassland, Savanna and Thicket Biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013); also sampled from maize fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zaire, Tanzania, Uganda, Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Humansdorp (-34.04, 24.78); Mazeppa Bay (-32.47, 28.64); Thyspunt 12 km WNW (-34.2056, 24.7083); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); Fort Fordyce Forest Reserve (-32.69, 26.51). **Free State:** Sterkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-28.48, 29.01). **Gauteng:** Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19); Bronkhorstspruit to Balmoral (-25.82, 28.87); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23); Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Nkandla Forest (-28.61, 31.09); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Sani Pass (-29.62, 29.37); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Royal Natal National Park (-28.73, 28.92); Wakefield Farm (-29.50, 29.90). **Mpumalanga:** Graskop (-24.93, 30.84); Wakkerstroom (-27.33, 30.14); Pilgrims Rest (-24.89, 30.75). **Western Cape:** Fernkloof Nature Reserve (Hermanus) (-34.61, 19.34); Keurboom Nature Reserve (-34.03, 20.41); Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve (-34.32, 18.96); Gondwana Game Reserve SE Herberdsdale (-34.07, 21.9); Katberg (-32.78, 26.62).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in >10 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Blandin (1977). Known from both sexes.

Chiasmopes lineatus from Keurboom Photo Eben Lourens

After Blandin (1977).

C. lineatus from Wakefield Farm Photo P. Webb

Palp and carapace Photo ASD

From Thyspunt Photo Linda Wiese

Chiasmopes namaquensis (Roewer, 1955)

COMMON NAME: Namaqua Chiasmopes Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Roewer (1955) as *Spencerella namaquensis* from Namibia. It has also been recorded from South Africa from three provinces (EOO=294 402 km²; AOO=24km²; 7-1663 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Sheet-web pisaurids that construct webs in vegetation close to the ground especially short shrubs and bushes but occasionally also between grass tussocks. They are active at night. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Had-dad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Free State: Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.8, 27.65); **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93; 31.02). **Western Cape:** Avontuur, Die Vlug (-33.72, 23.16); Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve (-34.32, 18.96); Table Mountain National Park New-lands Forest (-33.91, 18.42).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in the Mpetsane Conservation Estate, Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020) and Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Blandin (1977) and known only from the female. More sampling needed to collect the male.

Chiasmopes signatus (Pocock, 1902)

COMMON NAME: Grahamstown Chiasmopes Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described by Pocock (1902) as *Spencerella signata* from Grahamstown. The species is presently only known only from two localities (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 552 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species range. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient.

LIFESTYLE: Sheet-web spiders sampled from the Thicket Biome. Nothing more known about their behaviour.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Bathurst (-33.5, 26.84).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Blandin (1977). Known from both sexes. Distinguished from *S. lineata* from Durban by having the anterior lateral eyes two diameters instead of one diameter apart, the anterior medians about a diameter instead of half a diameter apart, and only equal to the radius of the posterior medians.

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After Blandin (1977).

Chiasmopes signatus from Bathurst Photo John Richter

GENUS *CISPIUS* Simon, 1898

The genus *Cispius* described by Simon (1898) is known from nine African species (World Spider Catalog 2020). Three species are recorded from South Africa

COMMON NAME: Cispius Nursery-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Cispius variegatus* Simon, 1898

MORPHOLOGY: Total size 7-8 mm. Carapace slightly longer than wide; narrower in eye region; eyes in two rows, anterior row more or less recurved; anteriorly eyes smaller than posterior eyes; three cheliceral teeth in most species. Abdomen oval decorated with patterns. Legs strong frequently banded.

LIFESTYLE: The capture web is sheet-like and composed of dense crisscrossing threads. At one end the web is drawn into a long funnel that descends into the base of a plant. They run on top of the web using scaffold lines. One specimen was also collected from a hole in bark.

TAXONOMY: Revised by Blandin (1987). He remarked that *Charminus* and *Cispius* are morphologically very similar.

Habitus after Blandin (1978)

Eye after Blandin (1978)

Three cheliceral teeth Photo ASD

Cispius sp. Photo Peter Webb

Cispius kimbius Blandin, 1978

COMMON NAME: Kimberley Cispius Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Blandin (1978) from Kimberley in the Northern Cape. The species is sampled also from Swaziland. In South Africa recorded from three provinces (EOO=356 064 km²; AOO=36 km²; 7-1332 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They construct a funnel like web in short shrubs and bushes close to the ground or in trees. The capture web is sheet like and composed of dense criss-crossing threads. At one end the web is drawn into a long funnel that descends into the base of a plant. They are active at night. Sampled from the Grassland, Nama Karoo and Savanna Biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92). **Free State:** Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-29.51, 25.25). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Hell's Gate (-28, 32.48); Fanie Camp (-27.9232.27); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24). **Limpopo:** Naboomspruit (-24.52, 28.70); Klein Kariba (-24.88, 28.29). **Northern Cape:** Kimberley (-28.73, 24.76).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve, Dukuduku Forest Station and Ndumo Game Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Only known from only the female.

Cispius kimbius female from Klein Kariba
Photo Peter Webb

Epigyne after Blandin (1978)

Cispius kimbius female from Bloemfontein
Photo Rudi Steenkamp

Cispius problematicus Blandin, 1978

COMMON NAME: Zaire Cispius Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Blandin (1978) from the Democratic Republic of the Congo. The species has also been sampled from South Africa and Swaziland. In South Africa recorded from two provinces (EOO=48 881 km²; AOO=32 km²; 116-1412 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore be listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They construct a funnel like web in short shrubs and bushes close to the ground or in trees. The capture web is sheet like and composed of dense criss-crossing threads. At one end the web is drawn into a long funnel that descends into the base of a plant. Sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Limpopo:** Klaserie Game Reserve Guernsey Farm, 15 km from Klaserie (-24.55, 31.02); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (Satara) (-24.38, 31.78); Kruger National Park (Sabiepoort) (-25.19, 32.2); Kruger National Park (Randspruit) (-25.28, 31.64).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. They are protected in the Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020) and the Luvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2008).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the male.

Cispius problematicus Photo Peter Webb

Cispius problematicus Photo ASD

Undescribed female?

Palp after Photo Blandin(1978)

Cispius variegatus Simon, 1898

COMMON NAME: Variegated Cispius Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Simon (1898) from the Democratic Republic of the Congo. The species is also sampled from South Africa from three provinces (EOO= 237 284 km²; AOO=28km²; 5-1498 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They construct a funnel-like web in short shrubs and bushes close to the ground or in trees. They are active at night. Sampled from the Forest, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Coffee Bay (-31.97; 29.14); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **Gauteng:** Irene (field opposite Gem Village) (-25.89, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Hell's Gate (-28, 32.48), Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Wakefield Farm (-29.4733, 29.8925). **Limpopo:** Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. The species is protected in the Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020), Kosi Bay Nature Reserve and Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2009).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Blandin (1978) and only known from the female.

After Blandin (1978)

Cispius variegatus from Irene Photo P. Webb

GENUS *EUPROSTHENOPS* Pocock, 1897

The genus *Euprosthénops* described by Pocock (1897) is known from nine species and one subspecies. Eight species are known from Africa and one species from India (World Spider Catalog 2020). Three species have been recorded from South Africa.

COMMON NAME: Euprosthénops Nursery-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Euprosthénops bayaonianus* (Brito Capello, 1867)

MORPHOLOGY: Carapace longer than wide; eyes in four rows 2:2:2:2; clypeus with blunt projection; anterior lateral eyes situated on projection; diameter AME < ALE; MOQ longer than or as long as posterior width; chelicerae with four posterior teeth. Abdomen elongate tapering to the back. Legs with spines on femur, tibia and metatarsi; patellae with one spine dorso-apically; three claws.

LIFESTYLE: They make large webs in vegetation with funnel at bottom. *Euprosthénops* moves under the web. The female carries the egg sac below the body and builds a nursery-web when spiderlings emerge.

TAXONOMY: Genus revised by Blandin (1976) with notes on some species by Silva & Sierwald (2014).

E. bayaonianus KZN Photo Andrea Sander

E. bayaonianus Photo Clarissa de Lange

E. australis

E. bayaonianus

E. proximus

E. australis female with egg sac Photo Nicolette Josling

Euprostenops australis Simon, 1898

COMMON NAME: African Euprostenops Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Simon (1898) from Hebron in the North West. The species has a wide distribution recorded from several African countries. In South Africa recorded from eight provinces (EOO=587 787 km²; AOO=128 km²; 4-1663 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Funnel-web pisaurids construct their webs in short shrubs and bushes close to the ground or large webs are made in trees. The capture web is sheet like and composed of dense criss-crossing threads with a funnel at the bottom. Sampled from the Grassland, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). Sometimes found in houses. Care of the egg sac and spiderlings was observed in Mpetsane (Jones 2016).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, Namibia, Nigeria, Zimbabwe, Zambia, Senegal and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **Free State:** Bethulie (-30.49, 25.99); Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Mpetsane Conservation Estate near Clocolan (-28.8, 27.65). **Gauteng:** Centurion (-25.85, 28.16); Hammanskraal (-25.41, 28.27). **Kwa-Zulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Estcourt (-29, 29.87); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Hell's Gate (-28.01, 32.48), Lake Sibaya (-27.35, 32.7); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Weenen (-28.84, 30.07); Zululand Lake Libagi (-28.33, 31.08); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.544, 32.155); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Farm Vergeval district Ngotsche (-28.92, 31.35). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park, Shingwedzi (-23.12, 31.43); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Platjan (-22.75, 28.49); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Saamboubrug (Farm Umvoti) (-22.92, 28.98); Zebediela (-24.31, 29.27); Lephalale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-23.12, 29.00). **Mpumalanga:** Barberton (-25.79, 31.04); Secunda (-26.5, 29.18); Nelspruit (-25.34, 31.77). **North West:** Hebron (-25.55, 28.02); Kgaswane Mountain Reserve (-25.72, 27.18); Grootplaas De Rust (-25.46, 27.50). **Northern Cape:** Kimberley (-28.73, 24.76); Rooipoort Nature Reserve Site 1 (-28.561, 24.162); Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (-27.3, 22.44).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Species protected in 11 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Blandin (1976). Known from both sexes.

Euprostenops australis Photo Linda Wiese

After Blandin (1976).

Euprostenops australis female with Photo Peter Webb

Euprostenops bayaonianus (Brito Capello, 1867)

COMMON NAME: Decorated Euprostenops Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Brito Capello (1867) as *Podophthalma bayonianna* from Mozambique. It has been recorded from several African countries. In South Africa recorded from six provinces (EOO=248 372 km²; AOO=32 km²; 415-1444 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Funnel-web pisaurids construct their webs in short shrubs and bushes close to the ground. Large webs are made in vegetation with a funnel at the bottom. The capture web is sheet like and composed of dense criss-crossing threads. Sampled from the Grassland, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zaire, Ivory Coast, Mozambique, Kenya, Ghana, Sierra Leone, Zambia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Kwandwe Private Game Reserve (-33.09, 26.57). **Free State:** Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-29.51, 25.25); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.8, 27.65). **Gauteng:** Irene (field opposite Gem Village) (-25.89, 28.23); Pretoria/ Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Wallmannsthal (-25.52, 28.3). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Drummond (-29.73, 30.73). **Limpopo:** Farm Elandsberg, between Warmbath/Thabazimbi (-24.73, 27.72); Tshulu (-22.58, 30.81); Tshipise Alicedale farm (-22.62, 30.14); Acacia Lodge Game Reserve Thabazimbi (-24.60, 27.38); Mabula Nature Reserve (-24.84, 27.96). **Mpumalanga:** Nelshoogte Forest Reserve (-25.83, 30.83).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Species protected in Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020), Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve, Kwandwe Private Game Reserve, Mpetsane Conservation Estate, Acacia Lodge Game Reserve and Nelshoogte Forest Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Blandin (1976). Known from both sexes.

After Blandin (1976).

E. bayaonianus from Drummond with ventral view anterior

E. bayaonianus from Mabula NR Photo Michael van Kal

Euprosthénops proximus Lessert, 1916

COMMON NAME: Tanzania Euprosthénops Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Lessert (1916) from Tanzania. The species has been recorded from several African countries. In South Africa sampled from four provinces including two protected areas: (EEO=47 985 km²; AOO=12 km²; 51-1251m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Funnel-web pisaurids construct their webs in short shrubs and bushes close to the ground or in trees. Large webs are made in vegetation with a funnel at the bottom. The capture web is sheet-like and composed of dense crisscrossing threads. Sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). Heidger (1988), in a study of spiders inhabiting abandoned mammal burrows at Nylsvley in South Africa, found that *Euprosthénops proximus* builds a web over that of the agelenid *Olorunia ocellata* or pholcid *Smeringopus pallidus*, attaching it to grass surrounding the burrow. The web is hammock-shaped and the spider sits in the middle in wait of prey. When disturbed, the spider runs over the web of the agelenid and escapes into the burrow.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Ethiopia, Ivory Coast, Rwanda, Tanzania and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-29.51, 25.25); **Gauteng:** Roodeplaar Research Station (-25.66, 28.35). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66). **Limpopo:** Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in the Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve and Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Blandin (1976). Known from both sexes.

After Blandin (1976).

Euprosthénops proximus female. Photo N. Josling

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After Lessert (1916)

GENUS *EUPROSTHENOPSIS* Blandin, 1974

The African genus *Euprosthensopsis* described by Blandin (1974) is known from seven species and one subspecies (World Spider Catalog 2020). Four of them are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAME: Euprosthensopsis Nursery-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Euprosthensopsis armata* (Strand, 1913)

MORPHOLOGY: Carapace as wide as long; anterior lateral eyes pedunculate, as in *Euprosthensopsis*, peduncles generally somewhat more detached from the cephalothorax; small base of the median eyes trapezium proportionally larger than in *Euprosthensopsis*; posterior margin of the chelicerae with 3 teeth; cephalothorax with pilosity forming a characteristic ornamentation: two thin white and more or less undulating lateral bands extend onto the median part of the peduncles of the anterior lateral eyes, the sides of which are brown; a thin white median band penetrating the eye group and connected by white stripes to the lateral bands (this characteristic was not observed on some specimens with poorly preserved pilosity, such as the *E. armatus* type specimens). Abdomen oval; tapering towards back. Legs relatively long, sometimes slightly laterigrade; three claws;

LIFESTYLE: *Euprosthensopsis* species forage on sheet-webs made low in vegetation and run on top of the sheet.

TAXONOMY: Revised by Blandin (1974) with notes on some species by Silva & Sierwald (2014).

Euprosthensopsis sp. from Bloemfontein Photo Johan van Zyl

Euprosthensopsis sp. webs in the field (Otter trail)

Euprosthensopsis sp. on web from Blyde River Photo W. Jerling

Euprostenopsis armata (Strand, 1913)

COMMON NAME: Euprostenopsis Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Strand (1913) as *Euprostenopsis armatus* from Lake Albert. It has been recorded from several African countries. In South Africa sampled from four provinces (EOO=90 545 km²; AOO=16 km²; 159-1663 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range in Africa the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Sheet-web pisaurids that construct their webs in bushes but occasionally also between grass tussocks. They run on top of the sheet-web. Sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013)

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, Tanzania, Uganda, Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Mpetsane Conservation Estate (near Clocolan) (-28.8, 27.65). **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19). **Limpopo:** Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67). **Western Cape:** Cederberg Wilderness Area (-32.4, 19.09).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species it is protected in the Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016), Mpetsane Conservation Estate and Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009).

TAXONOMIC NOTES. Revised by Blandin (1977). This species known from both sexes.

Euprostenopsis armata from Orangekloof Photo Rene Theron

After Blandin (1977).

Euprostenopsis armata from Mpetsane Photo Allen Jones

Euprostenopsis lamorali Blandin, 1977

COMMON NAME: Lamoral's Euprostenopsis Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Blandin (1977) from Kluhlmoe Reserve in KwaZulu-Natal. In South Africa recorded from single localities in three provinces (EOO=66 865 km²; AOO=12km²; 4-1345m a.s.l.). Although only known from one sex this species has a wide distribution and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Sheet-web pisaurids construct their webs in bushes but occasionally also between large grass tussocks. Sampled from the Fynbos, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92). *KwaZulu-Natal:* Zululand, Kluhlmoe Reserve (-28.33, 31.08). *Western Cape:* Borrelfontein 8 km W of Gouritz Mouth (-34.33, 21.85).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: This species known from only the female.

After Blandin (1977).

Euprostenopsis lamorali from Borrelfontein Photo ASD

Euprosthenoopsis pulchella (Pocock, 1902)

COMMON NAME: Common Euprosthenoopsis Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Pocock (1902) from Grahamstown in the Eastern Cape. The species has been recorded from Lesotho, Swaziland and South Africa countries. In South Africa sampled from six provinces (EOO=105 3167 km²; AOO=120 km²; 5-1557 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide range therefore listed as of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Sheet-web pisaurids construct their webs in bushes but occasionally also between large grass tussocks. They construct sheet webs in low vegetation. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Lesotho, Swaziland and South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cradock (-32.16, 25.61); Graaff-Reinet (-32.24, 24.53); Grahamstown /Makhanda Tea Fountain (-33.3, 26.52); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Thyspunt 12 km WNW Cape St Francis (-34.2056, 24.7083); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Tsolwana Nature Reserve (-32.171, 26.500). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (near Clocolan) (-28.8, 27.65). **Limpopo:** Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45). **Mpumalanga:** Blyde River (-24.27, 30.83); Kruger National Park (Pretoriuskop Numbi) (-25.140, 31.208); Kruger National Park (Pretoriuskop Shabeni) (-25.123, 31.237). **Northern Cape:** Kimberley (-28.73, 24.76); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17). **Western Cape:** Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45); Kommetjie (-34.16, 18.34); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Murrays- burg (-31.96, 23.75); Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21); Table Mountain National Park (Buffelsfontein) (-34.52, 18.76); Table Mountain National Park (Devil's Peak) (-33.92, 18.45); Table Mountain National Park (Signal Hill) (-33.90, 18.38); Hermanus (-34.40, 19.25); Fernkloof Nature Reserve (-34.61, 19.34); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (-23.67, 28.38); Kalk Bay (-34.19, 18.42); Cape Hout Bay (-34.04, 18.32); Bergvliet (-34.03, 18.63)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Sampled from more than 10 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Blandin (1977) and known from both sexes.

Euprosthenoopsis pulchella Photo Koos Geldenhuys

After Blandin (1977).

Euprosthenoopsis pulchella Photo E. Henderson

Euprostenopsis vuattouxi Blandin, 1977

COMMON NAME: Curvy-lined Euprostenopsis Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described Blandin (1977) from the Ivory Coast. It has been recorded from South Africa from seven provinces (EOO=752 851 km²; AOO=68 km²; 1-1478 m a.s.l.). This species is possibly under collected and is suspected to occur in the countries in-between Ivory Coast and South Africa. Due to its wide geographical range the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Sheet-web pisaurids construct their webs in bushes but occasionally also between large grass tussocks. They construct sheet webs in low vegetation. Sampled from the Grassland, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Ivory Coast, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mkambati Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97). **Gauteng:** Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.80, 28.77); Irene Veld field opposite Gem Village (-25.89, 28.23). **Free State:** Farm Doornkloof, Riemland (-27.87, 27.87). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Farm Elandsberg, between Warmbath/ Thabazimbi (-24.73, 27.72); Kruger National Park: Shingwedzi (-23.12, 31.43); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Naboomspruit (-24.52, 28.7); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (-24.98, 31.58). **Northern Cape:** Hantam Botanical Garden, Nieuwoudtville (-31.34, 19.19); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats. The species is sampled from eight protected areas: Mkambati Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2011), Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve, Ezemvelo Nature Reserve, Ndumo Game Reserve, Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019), Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020), Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008) and Tswalu Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: This species is known from both sexes.

After Blandin (1977).

Euprostenopsis vuattouxi female from Irene Photo Peter Webb

E. vuattouxi female from Roodeplaat Photo Peter Webb

GENUS *HYGROPODA* Thorell, 1894

The genus *Hygropoda* Thorell , 1894 is known from three African species(World Spider Catalogue 2020).

COMMON NAME: Green nursery-web spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Hygropoda prognatha* Thorell, 1894

MORPHOLOGY: Body size TL. Males and females of similar size . Colour: live specimens green. Carapace profile flat; clypeus steep; eyes in two rows; subequal in size with anterior lateral eyes smallest; eyes of poster eye row larger than those of the anterior row; median ocular quadrangle narrower anterior than posterior. Abdomen long and slender; tapering towards back. Legs very long; tarsi of males and females curving, pseudosegmented; trochanters with shallow notches.

LIFESTYLE: Aboreal diurnal and nocturnal spiders hunting on small sheet-webs over leaves in forest areas.

TAXONOMY: African species not revised.

Hygropoda sp. from Amanzimtoti Photo Bruce Blake

Hygropoda tangana (Roewer, 1955)

COMMON NAME: Green nursery-web spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Roewer (1955) as *Cispius tanganus* from Tanga in East Africa. The species also recorded from four African countries. In South Africa recorded from Eastern Cape (EOO<1000 km²; AOO=8 km²; 1-860m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range in Africa the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant dwellers sampled from foliage in the Savanna and Grassland Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Tanzania, Kenya, Madagascar and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No are significant threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Silva (2013). Known from both sexes.

After Roewer (1955)

After Silva (2013)

Hygropoda sp.

Not sure whether this species is the same as *Hygropoda tangana*.

From Woodbush Photo Peter Webb

From Amanzimtoti Photo Bruce Blake

GENUS *MAYPACIUS* Simon, 1898

The genus *Maypacius* described by Simon (1898) is known from nine African species. The genus is restricted to Africa. Four species are known from South Africa but not recorded as such on the World Spider Catalogue (2020).

COMMON NAME: Maypacius Nursery-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Maypacius bilineatus* (Pavesi, 1895)

MORPHOLOGY: Body size TL 10-12 mm. Carapace longer than wide; narrower in eye region; clypeus sloping with projections; anterior eye row strongly procurved; anterior lateral eyes not on tubercles but located nearly below the anterior median eyes; posterior eye row strongly recurved; cheliceral furrow with two teeth equal in size. Abdomen elongated, tapering towards back. Legs with three claws; relatively long.

LIFESTYLE: Occurs in the savanna, found in vegetation (Blandin 1978).

TAXONOMY: African species not revised but Blandin (1975) described some species.

After Blandin (1974)

Maypacius sp. Photo Peter Webb

Maypacius bilineatus (Pavesi, 1895)

COMMON NAME: Maypacius Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described Pavesi (1895) as *Tetragonophthalma bilineatus* from Ethiopia. The species has been recorded from several African countries. In South Africa sampled from four provinces (EOO=110 603km²; AOO=36 km²; 47-1310 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They make sheet-webs in vegetation and are active at night. Sampled from the Forest, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, Ethiopia, Madagascar, Mozambique, Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mkambati Nature Reserve (31.32, 29.97). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ntendeka Wilderness Area (-27.82, 31.42); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); iSimangaliso Wetland park Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park: (Shingwedzi 20 km N) (-22.9, 31.37); Kruger National Park (Satara KSSD3) (-24.38, 31.78); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (-24.98, 31.58).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in the Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008), Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009) and Mkambati Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2011).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Blandin (1975), known from both sexes.

Maypacius bilineatus female Photo Peter Webb

Maypacius bilineatus female Photo ASD

Maypacius christophei Blandin, 1975

COMMON NAME: Christoph's Maypacius Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Blandin (1975) from the Democratic Republic of the Congo. It has been recorded from three African countries. In South Africa known from the Gauteng (EOO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1247 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range in Africa and can be listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They make sheet-webs in vegetation and are active at night. Sampled from the Savanna Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Gauteng*: Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. More sampling needed to confirm the species range in South Africa.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from female.

After Blandin (1975)

Maypacius roeweri Blandin, 1975

COMMON NAME: Roewer's Maypacius Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described Blandin (1975) from Democratic Republic of the Congo. It has also been recorded from South Africa from three provinces (EOO=65 853 km²; AOO=20 km²; 295-1146m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range in Africa it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They make sheet-webs in vegetation and are active at night. Sampled from the Savanna Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Tswaing Nature Reserve (-25.41, 28.08). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Buzzard Mountain Retreat (-23.04, 29.91). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (Skukuza-Malelane) (-25.2065, 31.5790); Kruger National Park (Vutomi 09) (-24.61, 31.79).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species and it is protected in the Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019), Tswaing Nature Reserve and Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from male.

Maypacius roeweri from Buzzard Mountain Photo Dawn Cory Toussaint

After Blandin (1975)

Maypacius roeweri from Blouberg Photo ASD

Maypacius stuhlmanni (Bösenberg & Lenz, 1895)

COMMON NAME: Stuhlmann's Maypacius Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1895 from Tanzania. It has been recorded from three African countries. In South Africa sampled from Limpopo (EEO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1310 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They make sheet webs in vegetation. Sampled from the Savanna Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Tanzania, Zanzibar, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species and it is protected in the Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Blandin (1975). Known known only from female.

Maypacius stuhlmanni female Photo: SANSA VM

After Blandin (1975)

GENUS *NILUS* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876

The genus *Nilus* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876 is known from 18 species of which five are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAME: Nilus Fish-Eating Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Nilus curtus* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876

MORPHOLOGY: Body size TL female 11-27 mm, male 9-18 mm. Colour cryptic with the carapace frequently decorated with white longitudinal bands or symmetrical patterns. Carapace a little longer than wide; eyes arranged in two rows; with the anterior eye row recurved and slightly shorter than posterior median eyes; carapace usually with broad sub marginal bands on each side; as far from margin as width of band, not extending to the margin. Abdomen oval tapering to the back; ventral area usually pale. Legs relatively long, sometimes slightly laterigrade with numerous spines; three claws.

LIFESTYLE: *Nilus* spp. are free-living usually found at the edge of fresh-water ponds where they prey on fish and small invertebrates. The female usually carries the egg sac beneath her sternum held by her chelicerae and palpi. Just before the young emerge the female constructs a framework of silk, known as a nursery web, in which she deposits the eggs. After emerging from the egg sac the young stay in this nursery web before they disperse, hence their common name nursery-web spiders.

TAXONOMY: Genus was studied by Sierwald (1987, 1989,1990) and Jäger (2011).

Nilus massajae from Eshowe Photo Peter Webb

Nilus margaritatus female with egg sac from Bergpan Photo Peter Webb

Nilus sp. eye pattern Photo Hannes Mitchell

Nilus curtus

Carapace with band but not marginal; abdomen variable with white spots or marginal bands

Nilus margaritatus

Carapace with marginal band; sometimes with dark edge; abdomen variable sometimes with row of spots and or bands

Nilus massajae

Carapace with sub marginal band; abdomen with marginal stripes, sometimes with dark transverse bands.

Nilus radiatolineatus

Carapace variable with sub marginal bands or spots; abdomen with spots or dark transverse bands.

Nilus rossi

Carapace variable with marginal bands (not white); abdomen darker pattern on posterior border

Nilus curtus O.P.-Cambridge, 1876

COMMON NAME: Spotted Nilus Fish-Eating Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by O.P.-Cambridge (1876) from Durban in South Africa. It has been recorded throughout Africa. In South Africa sampled from six provinces (EOO= 88 522km²; AOO=72 km²; 15-1467m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Free running ground dwellers associated with fresh waters and known to catch small fish tadpoles and large aquatic invertebrates including insect nymphs or larvae. They can be found at fresh-water pools and were sampled from the Fynbos, Forest, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). Sierwald (1988) reported on the predatory, copulatory and parental behaviour of *N. curtus* a widespread and commonly collected species in the Afrotropical Region.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widely distributed throughout Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** East London (-33.01, 27.9). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.1); Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve (-29.47, 30.2); Zululand Ngxwala Hill (-28.33, 31.08); Alverstone near Hillcrest (-29.77, 30.73). **Limpopo:** Hoedspruit/ Hans Hohersen Wildlife Res Station (-24.65, 31.46); Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.52, 28.7); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (24.65, 28.67); Swadini Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Waterberg, Wilderness (-24.33, 28.33); Lephalale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71). **Mpumalanga:** Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31); Sabie (-25.1, 30.78). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); George (-33.95, 22.46); Table Mountain National Park: Cape Point (-34.41, 18.32).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in the De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009), Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020), Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006), Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve, Mosdene Nature Reserve, Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009) and Swadini Nature Reserve

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The species was studied by Sierwald (1983, 1984, 1987, 1989, 1990) and Jäger (2011). Previously known as *Thalassius spinosissimus*.

After Sierwald (1987)

Nilus curtus from Alverstone KZN Photo P. Webb

Nilus margaritatus (Pocock, 1898)

COMMON NAME: White Banded Nilus Fish-Eating Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Pocock (1898) as *Thalassius margaritatus* from Tanzania. It has been recorded from several African countries. Known from Swaziland and South Africa where it has been sampled from four provinces (EOO=380 040 km²; AOO=80 km²; 47-1247m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Free-running ground dwellers associated with fresh waters and known to catch small fish tadpoles and large aquatic invertebrates including insect nymphs or larvae. They can be found at fresh-water pools and have been sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Botswana, Kenya, Mozambique, Namibia, Tanzania, Zanzibar, Eswatini and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Crocodile River, Marico River (-26, 27.84); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Uvongo (-30.82, 30.39). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Lekgalameetsi Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Limpopo Valley Nature Reserve, near Pontdrift NW, Shashe River and Limpopo (-22.22, 29.13); Crocodile River Marico River (-24.19, 26.87); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Lekgalameetsi Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Kruger National Park (Punda Maria) (-22.68, 31.01); Lephalale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71); Buzzard Mountain Retreat (-23.04, 29.91). **Mpumalanga:** Lowveld National Botanical Garden (-25.47, 31.00); Kruger National Park (Sabiepoort 11) (-25.19, 32.2); Kruger National Park (Napi) (-25.37, 31.51); Kruger National Park (Makhuthwanini 04) (-25.38, 31.6); Kruger National Park (Skukuza-Malelane A04L) (-25.0672, 31.6212); Kruger National Park (Skukuza-Malelane A04U) (-25.0708, 31.6145); Kruger National Park (Skukuza-Malelane B02U) (-25.2119, 31.6228); Kruger National Park (Skukuza-Malelane B04U) (-25.1103, 31.6036); Kruger National Park (Skukuza-Malelane B03L) (-25.1094, 31.6235).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in >10 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Sierwald (1987). Known from both sexes.

Nilus margaritatus from Buzzard Mountain Retreat
Photo Dawn Cory Toussaint

N. margaritatus with egg sac
Photo Anka Eickhoff

After Sierwald (1987)

Nilus massajae (Pavesi, 1883)

COMMON NAME: Massajae Nilus Fish-Eating Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Pavesi (1883) as *Dolomedes massajae* from Ethiopia. It has been recorded from several African countries. In South Africa sampled from five provinces (EOO=778 775 km²; AOO=68 km²; 2-1467 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Free running ground dwellers associated with fresh waters and known to catch small fish tadpoles and large aquatic invertebrates including insect nymphs or larvae. They can be found at fresh-water pools and have been sampled from the Fynbos, Forest, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Malawi, Namibia, Uganda and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Farm Meredith, near Ugie (-31.09, 28.17); Kwelera Nature Reserve (-32.92, 28.06); Stutterheim (-32.54, 27.43); Hluleka Nature Reserve (-31.81, 29.28). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83); Eshowe (-28.89, 31.47). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Tshulu (Venda) (-22.58, 30.81); Waterberg, Donkerpoort Dam (-24.33, 28.33). **Mpumalanga:** Kaapsehoop (-25.56, 30.78); Sabie (-25.1, 30.78). **Western Cape:** Gouritsmond (-34.34, 21.87); Knysna, Goudveld State Forest (-34.03, 23.03); Groenefontein Nature Reserve (-33.65, 21.6); Stellenbosch, University Botanical Gardens (-33.93, 18.85); Uniondale (-33.66, 23.13); Rondegat (-33.26, 18.94); Borrelfontein 8 km W of Gouritz Mouth (-34.34, 21.87).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in the Kwelera Nature Reserve, Hluleka Nature Reserve, Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019), Goudveld State Forest and Groenefontein Nature Reserve

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Sierwald (1987). Known from both sexes.

After Sierwald (1987)

Nilus massajae from Eshowe Photo Peter Webb

Nilus radiatolineatus Strand, 1906

COMMON NAME: Nilus Fish-Eating Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Strand (1906) from Ethiopia. It has been recorded from several African countries. In South Africa sampled from five provinces (EOO=224 284 km²; AOO=28km²; 446-1712 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Free running ground dwellers associated with fresh waters and known to catch small fish tadpoles and large aquatic invertebrates including insect nymphs or larvae. They can be found at fresh-water pools and have been sampled from the Savanna Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Cameroon, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Ethiopia, Kenya, Namibia, Zimbabwe, Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38). **Limpopo:** Klein Kariba (-24.88; 28.29); Lephalale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71). **Mpumalanga:** Farm Goedehoop 182 (-26.16, 30.63). **Northern Cape:** Kimberley (-28.73, 24.76); Riverton (-28.52, 24.7). **North West:** Pilanesberg Nature Reserve (-25.25, 27.08).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species and it is protected in Pilanesberg Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Sierwald (1987). Known from both sexes.

Nilus radiatolineatus from Lephalale Photo Peter Webb

Nilus radiatolineatus Photo SANSA VM

Nilus rossi Pocock, 1902

COMMON NAME: White-Bum Nilus Fish-Eating Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Pocock (1902) from Durban. It has been recorded from four African countries. In South Africa sampled from four provinces (EOO=248 106 km²; AOO=52 km²; 7-1343m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Free-running ground dwellers associated with fresh waters and known to catch small fish tadpoles and large aquatic invertebrates including insect nymphs or larvae. They can be found at fresh-water pools and have been sampled from the Savanna Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, Mozambique, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27), Hell's Gate (-28, 32.48), Lake Sibayi (-27.33, 32.68); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.5444, 32.1546). **Limpopo:** Farm Elandsberg, between Warmbath/Thabazimbi (-24.73, 27.72); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Lephahlale (-23.67, 27.71); Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93); Legalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.17, 30.25). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-24.9898, 31.5926); Kruger National Park (Skukuza-Malelane C03L) (-25.4460, 31.5368). **North West:** Rustenburg (-25.65, 27.22).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in the Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020), Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006) and Legalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016).

TAXONOMIC NOTES Revised by Sierwald (1987). Known from both sexes.

After Sierwald (1987).

Nilus rossi from Lephahlale Photo Peter Webb

GENUS *PERENETHIS* L. Koch, 1878

The genus *Perenethis* L. Koch, 1878 is represented by six species of which two species, *P. simoni* and *P. symmetrica*, occur in Africa and both have been collected from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAME: Perenethis Nursery-Web Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Perenethis venusta* L. Koch, 1878

MORPHOLOGY: Body size TL 16 mm. Colour pattern: Median yellowish-brown, rarely red-brown; dorsal pattern with light lateral stripes along prosoma and opisthosoma enclose darker median sections; ventral pattern with greyish coloration of legs. Carapace very low, long and almost flat in lateral view; eye region curves down to chelicerae longer than wide; eyes not on tubercles; anterior row slightly procurved; posterior eye row recurved; eyes rather small and subequal; chelicerae with posterior margin with two unequally-sized teeth close to the inner part of the chelicerae. Abdomen elongate tapers to posterior end; with indistinct brownish markings laterally towards the posterior apex. Legs of median length, some specimens with thin, short pro- and retrolateral spines at the patella.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant dwellers found in savanna vegetation (Blandin 1975).

TAXONOMY: Revised by Blandin (1976) and Sierwald (1997).

Perenethis sp. Photo Dawn Cory Toussaint

After Blandin (1976)

Perenethis simoni (Lessert, 1916)

COMMON NAME: Simon's Perenethis Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Lessert (1916) as *Tetragonophthalma simoni* from Tanzania. It has been recorded from several African countries as well as from the Comoros. In South Africa sampled from four provinces (EOO=77 768 km²; AOO=48 km²; 47-1252 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They construct sheet-webs in vegetation. The species was sampled from the Savanna Biome (Blandin 1975). It has also been recorded from citrus orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widely distributed throughout Africa Tanzania, Mozambique, the Comoros and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35) **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); uMkhuze Game Reserve (-27.6093, 32.2273). **Limpopo:** Springbok Flats (Tuinplaas) (-24.9, 28.73); Naboomspruit (-24.52, 28.70); Makelali Game Reserve (-24.16, 30.69). **Mpumalanga:** Crocodile Valley Estate (-25.47, 31.03); Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31.00); Kruger National Park (Satara 07) (-25.38, 32.13); Kruger National Park (Skukuza-Malelane A02L) (-25.0851, 31.5145); Kruger National Park (Skukuza-Malelane A03L) (-25.0502, 31.5804); Kruger National Park (Skukuza-Malelane A04U) (-25.0708, 31.6145).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2009), Tembe Elephant Park, uMkhuze Game Reserve, Makelali Game Reserve (Whitmore et al. 2001) and Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Sierwald (1997) and known from both sexes.

Perenethis simoni Photo ASD

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Sierwald, 1997:

Perenethis symmetrica (Lawrence, 1927)

COMMON NAME: Namibia Perenethis Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Lawrence (1927) as *Tetragonophthalma symmetrica* from Namibia. The species has been recorded from several African countries. In South Africa sampled from four provinces (EOO=341 006 km²; AOO=28 km²; 91 -615 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They construct sheet-webs in vegetation. Sampled from the Fynbos and Savanna Biomes. Also sampled from maize (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, Djibouti, Kenya, Namibia, Senegal, Tanzania and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47). **Limpopo:** Klaserie Game Reserve Guernsey Farm, 15 km from Klaserie. (-24.55, 31.02); Kruger National Park (Shingwedzi, 20 km SE) (-23.22, 31.56). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (Skukuza Camp) (-25.00, 31.97); Kruger National Park (Lwakahle 08) (-25.43, 31.75). **Western Cape:** Kenilworth Racecourse Conservation Area (-34.25, 18.5); Table Mountain National Park (Orange Kloof) (-34.00, 18.24).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Species protected in the Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020)

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Sierwald (1997). Known from both sexes.

After Sierwald (1997).

Perenethis symmetrica male Photo ASD

GENUS *ROTHUS* Simon, 1898

The African genus *Rothus* Simon, 1898 is represented by three species.

COMMON NAME: Rothus Nursery-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Rothus purpurissatus* Simon, 1898

MORPHOLOGY: Total length: 11-12 mm. Members of the genus *Rothus* can be distinguished from all other African pisaurid genera by the following combination of characters: three cheliceral teeth on the retromargin; anterior eye row slightly procurved; posterior eye row recurved; wider than anterior eye row and distinct features in the male and female copulatory organs. In males the tegulum is large, with a pronounced anterior projection; the large and pointed conductor; the sickle-shaped embolus, and the median apophysis aligned and pointing almost horizontally retrolaterad. Retrolateral tibial apophysis elongated and with a divided tip. The female copulatory organs feature an anteriorly excavated middle field and prominent curved lateral lobes.

LIFESTYLE: They are free-running plant dwellers and found in vegetation. Active at night. Some species sometimes wander into residences

TAXONOMY: The African genus *Rothus* Simon, 1898 was reviewed by Silva & Sierwald (2015). The three currently accepted species (*R. auratus* Pocock, 1900, *R. aethiopicus* and *R. vittatus*) were illustrated and redescribed.

Rothus aethiopicus female with egg sac Photo Peter Webb

Rothus aethiopicus (Pavesi, 1883)

COMMON NAME: Common Rothus Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Pavesi (1883) as *Ocyale aethiopicus* from Ethiopia. The species has a wide distribution throughout Africa. In South Africa sampled from all the provinces (EOO=876 769 km²; AOO=196 km²; 4-1795 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range it is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They are free running plant dwellers and very commonly found on plants at night. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Succulent biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013). Also sampled from lucerne fields, pecans orchard and vineyards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Cameroon, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Ethiopia, Israel, Kenya, Mozambique, Rwanda, Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cwebe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.9); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Port Alfred (-33.58, 26.89); Queenstown (-31.89, 26.85); Wilgerskloof Farm, Bamboesberg, W Sterkstroom (-31.6, 26.37); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Clocolan, Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58); National Botanical Gardens, Bloemfontein (-29.05, 26.21); Sterkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-28.48, 29.01). **Gauteng:** Bedfordview (-26.18, 28); Benoni (-26.19, 28.31); Brakpan (-26.23, 28.37); Centurion, Irene (-25.85, 28.16); Johannesburg (-26.2, 28.04); Kempton Park (26.09, 28.23); Kemptonpark (Esther Park) (-26.1, 28.2); Pretoria/Tshwane: (-25.74, 28.19), Moreleta Park (-25.74, 28.19), Rietondale Research Station (-25.73, 28.23), Pyramid (-25.35, 28.37); Randburg (26.07, 27.92); Roodeplaat, Farm Leeufontein (-25.63, 28.34); Roodepoort, Lindhaven (-26.14, 27.86); Wonderboom (-25.68, 28.2); Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19); Faerie Glen Nature Reserve Pretoria (-25.7707, 28.3008); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08); Irene Veld field opposite Gem Village (-25.89, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Mooirivier (-29.2, 30); Ndumo Game Reserve, E shore of Shokwe Pan (-26.87, 32.24); Royal Natal National Park (-28.73, 28.92). **Limpopo:** Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Warmbaths/Bela-Bela (-24.88, 28.29). **Mpumalanga:** Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31); Wakkerstroom (-27.33, 30.14); Loskop Dam Resort (-25.42, 29.32).

Rothus aethiopicus from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Rothus aethiopicus with eggs Photo Peter Webb

After Blandin 1977

Rothus aethiopicus (continued)

North West: Makwassie (-27.3, 25.99); Mooivalleipark Potchefstroom (-27.17, 27.15); Broederstroom (-25.78, 27.87). **Northern Cape:** Kimberley (-28.73, 24.76); Nieuwoudtville, Oorlogskloof (-31.37, 19.11). **Western Cape:** Borrelfontein, 8 km W of Gouritz Mouth (-34.33, 21.85); De Hoop Nature Reserve, Potberg (-34.45, 20.44); Gamkaberg Nature Reserve (-33.31, 21.71); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Gamkaskloof) (-33.35, 21.67); Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21); Cederberg Wilderness Area 8.1 1325 masl (-32.43, 19.22); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Matjiesfontein (-33.24, 20.58).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in > 15 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Blandin (1977) and Silva and Sierwald (2015) and known from both sexes. The species was previously known as *R. purpurissatus*

After Blandin (1977)

Rothus aethiopicus Photo Dawn Cory Toussaint

Rothus aethiopicus Photo Nick Moerman

Rothus auratus Pocock, 1900

COMMON NAME: Garies Rothus Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1900 from Garies in the Northern Cape. Presently known from three provinces (EOO=144 180 km²; AOO=16 km²; 327-1307 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Plant-living nursery-web spiders that are found on vegetation at night. Their movements are erratic but they move swiftly on the substrate sometimes in leaps or jumps. *Rothus auratus* has been sampled from the Fynbos and Succulent Karoo biomes

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa: Eastern, Northern and Western Cape.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92). **Northern Cape:** Garies (-30.56, 17.97); Oorlogskloof Nature Reserve (-31.45, 19.1). **Western Cape:** Gouritsmond (Borrefontein, 8 km W) (-34.34, 21.87); Cederberg Crystal Pools Wupperthal (-32.34, 19.14).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in the Oorlogskloof Nature Reserve and Cederberg Wilderness Areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Silva and Sierwald (2015) and known from only the female, illustrated.

After Blandin 1977

After Silva and Sierwald (2015)

Rothus vittatus Simon, 1898

COMMON NAME: Cape Rothus Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Simon (1898) with type locality given only type as Cape of Good Hope. The species has been sampled from three provinces (EOO=203 759km²; AOO=40km²; 4-951m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They are free running plant dwellers and very commonly found on plants at night. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013), Nama Karoo and Thicket biomes. Also sampled from pistachio orchards.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa: Eastern Western and Northern Cape.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Graaff-Reinet (-32.24, 24.53); Grahamstown Tea Fountain (-33.3, 26.52). **Northern Cape:** Prieska (Farm Remhoogte) (-29.52, 23). **Western Cape:** Borrelfontein, 8 km W of Gouritz Mouth (-34.33, 21.85); Swartberg Nature Reserve, Gamkaskloof (-33.36, 21.69). Robben Island (-33.80, 18.35); Camps Bay (-33.95, 18.37); Hout Bay (-34.04, 18.32); Table Mountain National Park Platteklip Gorge (-34.04, 18.67); Plumstead Flats (-34.01, 18.46); Bergvliet (-34.03, 18.63).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in the Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005) and the Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Silva and Sierwald (2015) and known from only from the female.

Rothus vittatus female Photo Peter Webb

After Blandin (1977)

Rothus vittatus female Photo ASD

After Silva and Sierwald (2015)

GENUS *TAPINOTHELELLA* Strand, 1909

The monotypic genus *Tapinothelella* described by Strand (1909) is known only from two juvenile specimens that was described as *Tapinothelella laboriosa* Strand, 1909.

Tapinothelella laboriosa Strand, 1909

COMMON NAME: Tapinothelella Nursery-Web Spider

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Description based on a juvenile, no drawings provided.

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic describe by Strand (1909) from Miller's point Simonstown. Last sampled in 1903. The species is known only from a juvenile specimen and the genus is monotypic (EEO=4 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1m a.s.l.). The status of the species and genus remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect adult specimens to determine the species range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Miller's point Simonstown (-34.23, 18.47).

LIFESTYLE: Specimens were sampled from under stones.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: If the type material of the species could not be found it need to be listed as *nomia dubia*.

GENUS WALRENCEA Blandin, 1979

The genus *Walrencea* described by Blandin (1979) is monotypic and known from only one South African species.

COMMON NAME: This genus was named after Dr Lawrence according to Blandin (1979) therefore Lawrence's Nursery-web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Walrencea globosa* Blandin, 1979

MORPHOLOGY: Size TL 8-9 mm. Carapace: a little longer than wide; narrower in eye area; cephalic region broad; short fovea; carapace covered with pale setae; a white median line bordered by darker setae; number of teeth of the posterior margins of the chelicera variable (2 to 4); eyes eight in two rows; anterior row recurved; median ocular triangle longer than wide. Abdomen with a slightly dark abdominal folium (it is darker in the male); marked anteriorly with a short pale midline framed by dark setae; ventrum pale. Legs same colour as carapace; bearing strong setae.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant dweller.

TAXONOMY: Known only from original description.

Walrencea globosa female from Thyspunt Photo Linda Wiese

Walrencea globosa Blandin, 1979

COMMON NAME: Lawrence's Nursery-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Blandin (1979) from type locality only given as Natal. This is a monotypic genus. Although illustrated the description of species is poor and identification of species is still problematic. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living plant dweller. At Thyspunt a female was sampled from a silk retreat made in a dried branch.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: A specimen collected from the *Eastern Cape*: Thyspunt, 12 km WNW, Cape St Francis (-34.2056, 24.7083).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The status of the species is obscure and some more sampling is needed to determine the species range

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised known from both sexes, illustrated.

Walrencea globosa imm male Photo ASD

After Blandin 1979

Female was sampled from this retreat made in dried branches. Photo Linda Wiese

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